

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF AMBIENT TEMPERATURE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS UNDER KADUNA WEATHER CONDITIONS

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Abstract

This study investigates the effects of ambient temperature on the performance of a 100W solar photovoltaic system under the prevailing weather conditions of the Nigerian Defence Academy, Afaka, Kaduna. The photovoltaic module was set up at a tilt angle of 15°. The ambient temperature and humidity were measured hourly using the weather station between 9am to 5pm for 30 days from October 16, 2023. The results show that power output and efficiency decrease as ambient temperature increases. A strong positive correlation ($R = 0.79095$) was found between ambient and PV panel temperatures. Additionally, ambient temperature was found to have a moderate negative correlation with Voltage ($R = -0.4291$) and a strong negative correlation with power output ($R = -0.80519$). The analysis revealed that power output decreases with increasing ambient temperature. The simulation results validated the experimental findings, with percentage errors ranging from -21.63% to 16.01%. These findings have important implications for optimizing solar photovoltaic system performance in tropical regions.

Keywords: Solar System, Ambient Temperature, Monocrystalline, PV Solar Cell, Origin software

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1.0 Introduction

Energy is considered very essential for human survival. The consumed power per capita measures the standard of life and comfort in today's world, during the year (Pesch, Einarsdottir, Dillman, & Heinonen, 2023). Hence, the increasing global energy demand, coupled with the depletion of fossil fuels and the associated environmental pollution, has led to a growing interest in renewable energy sources. (Ang, et al., 2022; Zohuri, 2023; Holechek, Geli, Sawalhah, & Valdez, 2022). Solar energy, in particular, has emerged as a promising alternative to traditional energy sources due to its abundance and zero greenhouse gas emissions (Kakran, Raththore, Sidhu, & Kumar, 2024).

The PV system generates electrical power by converting solar radiation into direct electricity with the help of semiconductors that exhibit the photovoltaic effect. PV power generation employs solar panels constructed of several solar cells made of photovoltaic material. However, certain environmental and operational factors such as ambient temperature, water vapour, soiling, etc. contribute to the performance of the PV system since they are installed outdoors, and forced to work off design conditions owing to the fact that the PV cell is design under standard temperature condition of 25°C (Carlos, 2022; Achara & Yusuf, 2020; Hasan, Yousuf, Tushar, Das, & Islam, 2022) High temperatures can lead to a decrease in PV efficiency, while high water

vapor content can cause corrosion and damage to the PV modules (Ahmed, Maghami, Pasupuleti, Danook, & Basim Ismail, 2024)

There are many underperforming and failed photovoltaic solar systems in Kaduna, despite adequate sunshine available in this region all year-round (Isma'il, Jaro Ahmed, & Naibbi, 2016). One would expect the photovoltaic system to operate at maximum capacity. However, in practice, the system's performance is often suboptimal. The efficiency of the PV system drops as temperature rises, thereby reducing the power output generated (Carlos, 2022; Ahmed, Maghami, Pasupuleti, Danook, & Basim Ismail, 2024). This drop could frustrate the end users who rely on the system. Environmental factors such as ambient temperature, humidity variation, wind speed, shading, etc., contribute to the drop in performance of installed PV systems (Kaplanis, Kaplani, & Kaldellis, 2023; Shaik, Lingala, & Veeraboina, 2023). Until now, several researchers have focused on investigating the effect of the factors individually. However, the PV system is subjected to a simultaneous effect of the factors while in operation. Therefore, it is in this light that this study seeks to analyze the combined effect of temperature and water vapour content variation on the performance of solar photovoltaic systems installed under Kaduna weather conditions.

The study aims to investigate the effect of temperature on the performance of solar

photovoltaic systems under prevailing Kaduna weather conditions, to determine the effects of ambient temperature on the PV module hourly.

2.0 Literature Review

(Sanusi, Fajinmi, & Babatunde, 2011), Investigated the performance of an Amorphous Silicon Photovoltaic system in a tropical area of Ogbomosho, Nigeria. This study examines the impact of ambient temperature on system performance over 3 years, analyzing how temperature fluctuations affect its efficiency and overall operation. The authors used three functional flat plates PV modules of the same material containing 72 amorphous silicon solar cells, all connected in parallel and mounted horizontally on a metal frame. A variable resistor of 5.7 k Ω was employed as a load. The results revealed that the power output is directly proportional to the ambient temperature, and it was confirmed from the values of the correlation coefficient that when that was done, they yielded 85%, 86%, and 89% for the period under review. However, other types of PV modules and environmental factors were not considered; also, the measuring equipment used is not as recent as the one available now. They used a five-in-one Auto Raging Digital Multimeter (serial number M58209) in the year 2011.

(Akonjom & Njok, 2022), Studied the effect of meteorological parameters on the performance of photovoltaics installed under the Guinea Savannah atmosphere in Ogoja, Cross River State, to track and determine the maximum

power, voltage, and current produced by the photovoltaic module. A 130W polycrystalline module, a digital power tester of model WS400A, SM206, a digital hygrometer model KT-908, and an infrared gun were used for the study. The PV module was installed horizontally on a one-meter structure, and readings were recorded at an interval of 30 min from 6.00 am to 6.00 pm daily for 90days. The investigation shows that voltage stability was achieved between relative humidity levels of 67% to 47%, and there was a quick drop in voltage at relative humidity below 47%. Furthermore, the average temperature of 26.78°C for the location under study favours the mean panel temperature, which may not exceed 40°C for the months besides January, making it possible for the PV module to get close to 90%. Also, with an altitude of 85m above sea level, power usually gets close to 800W/m², making the location suitable for solar farms. However, the study was not specific as to what type of modules were best for the location, since only the polycrystalline ones were used.

(Ebhota & Tabakov, 2022), Studied the influence of photovoltaic cell technologies and elevated temperature on photovoltaic system performance, used a hypothetical 6-kWp capacity PV system, which was rooftop mounted, and monitored the performance of a PV system for different PV cell technologies and ambient temperatures. They firstly considered (crystalline silicon (c-Si)), which is of the first generation and then (copper indium

gallium selenide (CIGS)) of the second generation of PV cells. Ambient temperatures of 10 to 50 range, at an interval of 5 , were used to determine the influence of temperature on PV system performance, using the chosen PV cells. PVsyst was used as design software and for simulation. The results show that the CIGS PV Cell had the highest energy production at Standard Test Conditions (STC) and elevated temperature. At the same time, Crystalline Silicon produced the same amount of energy. The CIGS and Si monocrystalline PV cells have the highest and lowest PR, respectively.

(Booker, 2018), analyzed temperature and humidity effects on horizontal photovoltaic panels by constructing 40 test systems, each consisting of a 25W monocrystalline and 50W polycrystalline, temperature and humidity probe, a satellite communication model, a central processing unit, using a control system manufactured by the Air Force Institute of Technology in the United States to monitor power production, with a test site at 38 locations around the world, putting into account the primary climate type. Multivariate regression analysis established A statistical relationship between photovoltaic power output, ambient temperature, and humidity. Firstly, using a formulated model to characterize power output recorded after 15 min, it was applied to specific weather conditions with a general inaccuracy. More tailored or specific-location models were applied with varying accuracy, which gives a clue on the energy output of several locations

that may guide project decision-making in the future. However, it was found that more predictor variables are needed to improve model accuracy. The research did not clearly define the locations of the study.

(Shukla, Kant, Sharma, & Biwole, 2017), carried out a review of cooling methodologies of photovoltaic modules for enhancing electrical efficiency, considering techniques such as natural and forced air cooling, hydraulic cooling, heat pipe cooling, cooling with phase change material and thermoelectric cooling. They stated that the PV cells can absorb up to 80% of solar radiation from the sun. However, only a tiny fraction of the Incident absorbed radiation is converted to usable electricity, while a sizable amount of the radiation increases the temperature of the PV. This implies that high solar radiation and ambient temperature can impact the usable lifetime of the PV cell and the power generated from it. The review agrees that the PV module temperature is regulated by cooling, and hence, efficiency is improved. However, from the above review, the study focused more on solar radiation and ambient temperature without considering other environmental factors such as relative humidity, Water Content, Vapour, etc.

(Gholani, et al., 2023), investigated the impact of harsh weather conditions on solar photovoltaic cell temperature through experimental and analytical analyses, and thermal-optical modelling by adopting an

outdoor measurement experiment, an indoor control experiment, proposed multivariable linear regression, and a thermal-optical modelling of the module for comparison and validation. A standardized proposed empirical correlation; Beta coefficients of 0.541, 0.645, -0.035, -0.055, and -0.068 with a photovoltaic cell temperature determination coefficient of 0.728, 0.970, 0.972, 0.973, and 0.974 were used. The study found that cell temperature depends directly on irradiation and ambient temperature, and inversely on humidity, wind speed, and dust on the PV surface. Also, simulation results, correlation predictions, and experimental measurements show consistency when compared. In addition, the correlation form is most preferred in terms of prediction precision, simplicity, and computational cost. However, the thermal-optical modelling could predict the temperature distribution and provide more details. However, the study focused on the optical impact of dust on the transmission coefficient, and not much was said about the impact of humidity.

(Oyerinde, Suleiman, Akor, & James, 2022), Investigated the effect of temperature on solar photovoltaic power generation. The researchers adopted a 200W and 100W solar panel for the investigation, and the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering of the Kaduna Polytechnic was used as the site location for the experimentations. The characteristic parameters short circuit current (ISC), Open Voltage Circuit (VOC), and Maximum Power

(Pmax) were determined by Variation in PV module temperature with water being sprayed on it at ambient temperature and constant irradiation. An Arduino Uno Microcontroller type with 14 digital input/output pins, 6 analogue inputs, a 16 MHz quartz crystal, a USB connection, a power jack, a header, and a reset button was used to collect data. From the results, it was observed that the power output of the modules improved by decreasing the module temperature, which implies that, by cooling the photovoltaic system, the system's efficiency is increased.

Understanding the effect of ambient temperature on the performance of solar power systems in Kaduna will benefit the body of knowledge, thereby providing the engineer with necessary information to design and produce systems that can withstand harsh weather variations with improved power output and performance.

(Abbas, Harijan, Shaikh, Walasai & Ali, 2017), analyzed the effect of ambient temperature and relative humidity on Solar PV system performance using Quaid-e-Azam Solar Park, Pakistan, at Bahawalpur, Punjab. The authors employed an outdoor measuring device to measure the respective metrological parameters. The modules were installed southward fixed at an angle of 28° with horizontal, and the PV characteristics parameters were measured using a variable resistance and a Multimeter, as well as a pyrometer to measure Solar irradiance hourly

for the period under the study. From the results, it has been observed that the correlation between efficiency and temperature is higher than that between efficiency and relative humidity, and this shows that temperature is of great importance when considering the area at the early stage of the system design. The correlation coefficient for temperature and relative humidity was 83% and 64%, respectively, with a confidence level of 90%. The study area in Afaka, Kaduna, Nigeria, is characterized by unique climatic conditions and weather variations. Therefore, real-time data measurement was necessary for accurate comparison and drawing meaningful conclusions.

(Bhattacharya, Chakraborty, & Pal, 2014), In Tripura, India, researchers investigated the effects of ambient temperature and wind speed on the performance of a monocrystalline solar photovoltaic module. The work was carried out between 2012 and 2013 using a solar module no 03018119 of a maximum power of 37W manufactured by M/S Tata BP Solar India Ltd, a Digital Multimeter, MS2101, anemometer and a TENMARS TM-207 solar power meter were used to measure the I_{sc} and V_{oc} , ambient temperature, wind velocity, and solar radiation

intensity, and using a portable statistical 8 software to show to what extent ambient temperature and wind velocity has on the solar module as well as its correlation with efficiency. It was observed from the analysis that there is a direct proportionality between the ambient temperature and the Module efficiency. The correlation coefficient is 96% and 68% for ambient temperature and wind velocity. The results reveal a strong positive linear relationship between the module efficiency and ambient temperature and a moderate positive linear relationship between the module efficiency and wind velocity. However, the researcher only concentrated on ambient temperature and wind velocity without considering other regional meteorological parameters like relative humidity. Also, Tripura's weather conditions differ from those of Afaka, Kaduna, Nigeria.

3.0 Materials and Methods

3.1 Materials

The materials employed in this research work are thus presented:

- i. Solar Monocrystalline Module with the Electrical Characteristics shown in Table 3.1

Table 3.1 Photovoltaic Module specification at Standard Test Condition (STC)

Specification at STC (1000W/m ² , AM 1.5, 25°C)	
Maximum Power (P _{max})	100W
Maximum Power Voltage (V _{mp})	19.43V
Maximum Power Current (I _{mp})	5.15A
Open Current Voltage (V _{oc})	23.3V
Short Circuit Current (I _{sc})	5.51A
Maximum Series Fuse	10A
Operating Temperature	-20°C - 90°C

- ii. 20 mm x 20 mm angle iron for panel rack sourced from Kaduna Market
- iii. Multi-Contact, 4mm (MC4) Connector Sourced from the Kaduna market
- iv. PVsyst Software version 7.4.7
- v. Microsoft Excel 2019 was used in harmonizing the collected results
- vi. Origin Pro Software 2024 for graphing and the determination of the correlation value

S/N	Equipment	Specification	Model of Equipment	Brand	Source
1	Wireless Colour Forecast Station	Indoor and Outdoor Temp. range 0 to 50 / -40 to 60 degrees Celsius		La Crosse Technology	Lagos
2	Digital Multimeter	Voltage: AC 750V	MAS830L	Mastech	Kaduna
3	Techno Spark 7P	RAM: 4.00GB	TECHNO KF7j	Techno	Kaduna

3.2 Equipment

The equipment employed for this research work is shown in Table 3.2

Table 3.2: List of equipment

3.3 Methods

3.3.1 Site Description

The investigation is conducted at NDA Afaka Igabi local government area with a Tropical Savannah Climate corresponding to the Koppen Geiger climate classification with a population size of 636,400 as of 2022 projection and 3,222km² (Kottek, Griesser, Beck, Rudolf, & Rubel, 2006). Having a latitude of 10.61 N and Longitude of 7.31 E, Kaduna state, a state in the northwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria is the 8th largest city in the country as of 2006 with an area of 46,053km² (Nigeria, 2022) created in 1967 as a north central state which Zamfara, Katsina, and Kano bordero the north, Bauchi and Plateau

state to the east, Nassarawa State to the South and Niger State to the west also having Abuja Capital territory bordered to the southwest (Ota, Ecoma, & Wambu, 2020).

3.3.2 Experimental Setup

The PV module with a total area of 0.648m² was placed on a mounting structure as shown in plate 3. The mounting structure was constructed at the NDA Mechanical Engineering Department with an adjustment for several angles to absorb the sun's irradiation. A 100W monocrystalline PV panel was used for the experiment. The PV module was made to face south, without shading, to give room for collecting enough

solar radiation. The experimentation was carried out between October and November 2023, specifically from October 16 to November 24 2023, excluding the weekends.

3.3.3 Experimental Procedures

The PV module, as stated earlier in the experimental setup, was mounted on the mounting structure at a tilt angle of 15 facing south without any form of shading or shadow to examine the Voltage, current, temperature and water vapour content regarding their variations. The experiment was conducted from sunrise to sunset (Morning to Evening). The experiment commenced on October 16 2023, with data collection from 9am to 5pm daily for 30 days excluding weekends, the data was collected hourly to ascertain the actual behaviour of the site under investigation.

3.3.3.1 Method for Investigating the Effect of Ambient Temperature (Ta)

To determine the effect of ambient temperature, the experiment was conducted using a 100W PV panel with characteristics as displayed in the material section, the PV panel was placed in an outdoor environment to expose it to natural ambient temperatures as shown in plate 3.2, a total of 270 data points were collected over the 30day period with 9 data point collected per day as mentioned earlier measured on an hourly basis. A wireless weather forecast and a digital multimeter were used to measure the ambient temperature, Voltage and Current. The data collection schedule is summarized in Table 3.1.

The data collected during the experiment were analyzed using Origin statistical software. The PV Panel's performance parameters were plotted against the ambient temperature to ascertain the effect of temperature on the PV performance. Correlation analysis also determined the relationship between the PV Panel performance parameter and the ambient temperature. Due to the size of the results, day one of the temperature readings was analyzed, while the remaining results are shown in the appendices

3.3.3.2 Calculation of Photovoltaic Panel Efficiency

Efficiency measures how effectively a system, process, or device converts input energy or resources into useful output or desired results. It is a dimensionless quantity, often expressed as a percentage. Equation 1 is applicable for calculating the efficiency of a PV panel (Brockway, Sorrell, Semieniuk, Heun, & Court, 2021; Kellogg, 2023).

$$= \left(\frac{P}{E \cdot A} \right) * 100\% \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

η = Efficiency (%)

P_{out} = Output power of the PV module (W)

P_{in} = Incident solar power (W)

3.4 Statistical Analysis Methods

Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) was used to determine relationships between ambient temperature, WVC, and PV performance. Correlation coefficients (R-values) were

computed using Origin Pro Software to assess the strength of relationships. Error analysis was performed to evaluate the consistency of experimental results.

3.5 Simulation Methods

The PVsyst 7.4.7 simulation software was utilized to investigate the performance of the output of the PV panel at different temperatures by first generating an input file for the simulation containing the meteorological data in hourly values. The data used by the PV module was based on standard test conditions (STC) with a parameter of $1000\text{W}/\text{m}^2$ irradiance, at a temperature of 25C and an Air mass of 1.5.

3.6 PVsyst Simulation Procedure

The following procedures were followed for the

simulation:

- The PVsyst software was launched by double-clicking on the App.
- A new project was created in the open dialogue box by selecting the location, system type, and other basic parameters.
- The system layout was defined in terms of the configuration, that is, the number of modules selected as one.
- The Meteorological data source was selected from Meteonorm 8.1
- The simulation was run, and the results are displayed on the PVsyst. Platform. The results were later imported into Microsoft Excel for analysis.

Screenshots of the window settings of analysis, Project location, orientation, and module selection are shown in Plate 1, Plate 2, Plate 3, and Plate 4, respectively.

Plate 1: Screenshot PVsyst input data page.

Plate 2: Screenshot of NDA site as presented by the software.

3.7 Experimental Conditions

The study was conducted under real-time environmental conditions, ensuring that temperature and humidity fluctuations were natural and unaltered. Measurements were taken during the dry season, characterized by high ambient temperatures and variable humidity levels.

3.8 Calibration of Instruments

The wireless weather station was calibrated weekly using a standard reference thermometer and hygrometer to ensure accurate data collection. The digital multimeter was tested against a calibrated voltage reference before each measurement session. The solar PV module's performance was cross-checked with factory specifications to verify efficiency.

3.9 Data Validation

Measured data were compared with historical climate records from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMet). Simulated data from PVsyst were compared with experimental results, and percentage errors were calculated. The study's findings were cross-referenced with existing literature to ensure consistency and accuracy.

Plate 3: Experimental setup.

Plate 4: Experimental setup.

4.0 Results and Discussions

4.1 Effect of Ambient Temperature on PV Performance

The result of the measured data of ambient temperature for day one is displayed in Table 4.1

Table 4.1 Day One Measured data of Ambient Temperature.

S/n	Time Hr	Ambient temp. (Ta)	PV Panel Temp. (Tp)	Voltage V	Current A	Power Output W	Efficiency (%)
		°C	°C				
1	9:00	29.20	32.30	23.00	2.96	68.08	13.13
2	10:00	30.40	31.60	23.30	3.32	77.36	14.92
3	11:00	32.10	34.80	23.20	3.98	92.34	17.81
4	12:00	33.00	39.10	22.90	3.85	88.17	17.01
5	13:00	32.30	40.30	22.70	3.76	85.35	16.46
6	14:00	32.30	38.20	22.60	2.33	52.66	10.16
7	15:00	32.40	42.40	22.40	2.10	47.04	9.07
8	16:00	31.70	33.90	23.10	1.08	24.95	4.81
9	17:00	30.70	31.40	22.80	0.68	15.50	2.99

Temperature on PV Panel for Day One

Figure 4.1 Variation of ambient temperature, PV Panel temperature with time for day 1

4.3 Correlation of Ambient Temperature with PV Panel for Day One

Figure 4.2 Correlation analysis for ambient temperature with PV panel temperature.

Figure 4.1 depicts the variation of ambient and PV panel temperatures over time. It can be observed from the graph above that the ambient temperature influences the PV Panel temperature; it can be seen that the ambient temperature changes from 29.20°C at 9:00am, and as the PV Panel gets exposed to the sun, the PV Panel temperature immediately rises to 32.30°C. The highest Ambient Temperature is at 12:00pm, having 33.00°C with a PV panel Temperature of 39.10°C. However, the implication of the observed outcome rise at 15.00pm with 42.40°C at 32.40°C ambient

temperature, this was as a result of the prolonged stay of the PV panel under the sun. The implication of the above is that as Ambient Temperature increases, heat is built up on the PV Panel, and this is in agreement with Figure 4.2 showing a strong correlation between the ambient temperature and PV panel temperature, with the strength of the correlation R as 0.79095, which is a positive correlation. This indicates that, as ambient temperature increases, the PV Panel temperature also increases. This agrees with the work carried out by (Gholani et al., 2023; Qu, Gao, Kong, & Xu, 2024).

4.4 Ambient Temperature with Voltage for Day One

Figure 4.4 Variation of ambient temperature, voltage with time for day 1

4.5 Correlation of Ambient Temperature with Voltage for Day One

Figure 4.4 Correlation analysis for ambient temperature with voltage

Figure 4.3 shows the ambient temperature, voltage and time graph. The graph reveals the change in voltage, which results from the change in the ambient temperature. As the temperature remains constant from 13.00pm to 15.00pm at 32.30°C, the voltage increases due to the above drop. It was observed during the experimentation that the highest voltage was at 23.30V at 30.40°C and the lowest was at 22.40V at 32.40°C. There was an irregular change in voltage due to weather conditions that day.

However, Figure 4.4 is the correlation graph, which reveals that voltage decreases as the ambient temperature increases with a correlation Coefficient (R) of -0.4248, indicating a moderate negative correlation between Ambient Temperature (Ta) and Voltage. The obtained results agree with those in the literature (Shukla, Kant, Sharma, & Biwole, 2017; Gholani et al., 2023; Bhattacharya, Chakraborty, & Pal, 2014).

4.6 Ambient Temperature with Current for Day One

Figure 4.5 Variation of ambient temperature, current with time for day 1

Figure 4.5 above displays the graph of Ambient Temperature, Current and Time. The graph shows that as temperature increases, the Current tends to slightly increase as well the maximum current reach was 3.98A at 11:00am and the least Current generated for the day was 0.68A at

17:00pm, due to the amount of solar insolation reaching the PV Panel, indicating that temperature alone does not impact current generation. This result is similar to the results obtained in the literature. (Sher, Ahmed, Sattar, Ghafoor, & Shah, 2023; Samah, et al., 2023).

4.7 Ambient Temperature with Power Output for Day One

Figure 4.6 Variation of ambient temperature, power output with time for day one

4.8 Correlation of Ambient Temperature with Power Output for Day One

Figure 4.7 Correlation analysis of power output with ambient temperature

It can be seen from Figure .6 that the maximum power output generated for the day as the Ambient temperature progresses was 92.34W at 11am. As the temperature rises above STC, the power starts to drop. The lowest power obtained was 15.50W at 17:00pm due to reduced solar radiation. It can also be seen that th4e power output drops as time progresses and the PV Panel gets hotter. Figure 3.7 shows a strong negative correlation of -0.8519, which agrees

with Figure 3.6 above, and the obtained result is comparable to the literature (Oyerinde, Suleiman, Akor, & James, 2022).

4.9 Results of PV Panel Simulation on PVsyst Software

The results obtained from the simulation of the panel using PVSyst are discussed in the following section.

4.10 Results of Current-Voltage (I-V) Curve

Figure 3.8 I-V Curves, temperature of PV panel at 1000W/m² Irradiance

4.11 Results of Power-Voltage (P-V) Curve

Figure 4.9 P-V Curves Temperature of PV panel at 1000W/m² Irradiance

4.12 Temperature distribution graph

Figure 4.10 Array temperature distribution during running.

It can be seen from Figure 4.10 that; the influence of temperature on current and voltage at varying temperature at constant 1000W/m² irradiance it can be seen that, at temperature of 10 C voltage yielded 105W as power Output, at temperature of 25 C (STC) Power Output reduced to 99.7W the trend continues downward with the least Power Output of 81.5W at 70 C Figure 4.9 reports the drop in

Power Output as Temperature Increase while Figure 4.10 shows the movement of temperature over the PV Panel, However, there was a slight increase in Current consistently while the voltage decreases and that has impacted the overall Power Output generation of the system. The simulated results are in agreement with the measured data as well as those in the literature (Tripathi, Ray, Aruna, & Prasad, 2021) .

4.13 Comparison of Simulated Data with Measured Data

Table 4.2 Comparison of PVsyst Simulated value with Measured value

S/N	Parameter	Measured Value (MV)	Simulated Value (SV)	Percentage Error= (SV – MV)/MV x100
1	Temperature (°C)	31.90	25	-21.63
2	Water Vapour Content (kg/m ³)	183.01	212.49	16.01
3	Power Output (W)	94.66 W	99.7	5.39
4	Efficiency (%)	14.00	15.38	5.34

Table 4.2 above shows that the simulated values are in reasonable agreement with the measured value, with a percentage error ranging from - 21.63% to 16.01%. However, it is important to consider the difference between the STC and actual environmental conditions during the experiment. The table also reveals that the simulated temperature is lower than the measured value of 31.90°C due to the standard test condition (STC). However, on the other hand, Simulated Power Output and Efficiency values agree with the measured values with a percentage error of 5.39% and 5.34%. In this

regard, it can be said that, to some extent, the simulation software can accurately capture the solar photovoltaic system's performance under various environmental conditions.

5.0 Conclusion

The conclusion of the studies is as follows: The effects of ambient temperature on PV module performance revealed an important relationship between ambient temperature and the system's performance. Specifically, ambient temperature was found to have a strong positive correlation with PV panel temperature (R =

0.79095). Additionally, ambient temperature was found to have a moderate negative correlation with Voltage ($R = -0.4291$) and a strong negative correlation with power output ($R = -0.80519$).

The simulation results showed reasonable agreement with measured data, with percentage errors ranging from -21.63% to 16.01%. This validates the results obtained from the simulation with the experimental results on-site. Furthermore, the integration of locally sourced materials, such as groundnut shell biomass and cassava starch as binders, highlights the stove's cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability. Adopting such stoves can significantly reduce reliance on traditional biomass fuels, promote cleaner energy alternatives, and address public health and environmental challenges in rural and suburban regions. This project underscores the potential of innovative design and local resources to meet global energy needs sustainably.

Author's Contribution Statement

Lucky Augustine: Writing – original draft, Software, experimentation, Methodology, data analysis. **Dr. W. C Solomon:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Prof. Samaila Umaru:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors report no financial conflicts of interest related to this article's research, authorship, or publication.

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